

GUIDED WAVE-BASED INVERSE IDENTIFICATION TECHNIQUE FOR DAMAGES IN CF/EP COMPOSITES USING NEURAL NETWORK ALGORITHM

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ABSTRACT A structural health monitoring approach, combining the model-based numerical simulation with non-model-based information processing techniques, was developed for the identification of impact-induced damages in CF/EP composites. Guided Lamb wave propagation in the quasi-isotropic laminates under various damage situations was simulated, and corresponding spectrographic characteristics were purified, extracted and further compressed over the time-frequency domain via the wavelet transform, referred to as ‘*Digital Damage Fingerprint*’, which were then utilised for the *offline* development of an artificial neural network-based damage parameters database, supervised by an error-backpropagation (BP) neural algorithm. The proposed scheme and network were then *online* validated by identifying hole-type damages in CF/EP quasi-isotropic composite laminates, aided with an active online diagnosis system. Excellent quantitative identification (presence, location, size and orientation) for the hole-type damages in the CF/EP laminates has been achieved.

Key Words: Lamb wave, damage detection, FEM, wavelet transform, artificial neural network

1. INTRODUCTION

Structural health monitoring is axiomatically known as a hierarchical inverse analysis. For basic satisfaction, it is essential to determine whether damage has occurred or not in the structures; furthermore, the prediction for damage location and severity is required; while at the highest level, the residual safe life of the surveilled system is expected to be estimated. The first two levels are categorised as damage identification. Numerous and diverse approaches have been well documented over years, and amongst them the identification technique based on the pattern recognition have been recently emerged as one encouraging solution. The philosophy of pattern recognition is grounded on the fact that the structural responses can be parameterised as characteristic patterns, and refined into a representation where variations due to damage are highlighted [1]. The recognition for singularity or damage could thus be fulfilled by comparing the captured characteristic pattern for the systems under inspection with those of the counterparts that have been preliminarily identified for various damage states. Integrating the pattern recognition concept and specific biological principles, artificial neural network (ANN), regarded as a novel information processing method, operates as a novel computational model to authentically associate the high-order nonlinear responses with damage parameters for a given engineering system, while avoiding the tanglesome modelling.

Pilot studies [2-8] have demonstrated the uncontroversial advantage of ANN technique in damage assessment. However, in spite of their prosperous applications, currently existing ANN-based methods, where modal information or static data are widely used for the network training, have been more and more disputed due to the relative insensitivity of those data to undersized defects or consecutive extension of damages in a single time or frequency domain. Motivated by this, a damage

prediction technique for CF/EP laminates was developed in this study. An ANN was constructed relying on the dynamic spectrographic features for fundamental Lamb modes extracted in a dual-parameter (time-frequency) space. A signal processing package and an active online damage diagnosis system were developed. Their validity was practically examined by identifying hole-type damages in the laminates. The scheme is ultimately aimed at improving the survivability and reliability for *in-service* composite structures.

2. TRAINING DATA PREPARATION

In the previous study [9], both theoretical investigation and experimental verification have indicated that the spectrographic features of fundamental Lamb modes over the time-frequency space is quantitatively sensitive to the damages existed in the composite materials during their propagating. To exploit this property, the spectrographic characterisations of the Lamb wave energy spectrum in a composite laminate with various damage cases were evaluated over a dual-parameter (time-frequency) domain, and further extracted for the training of the artificial neural network.

The CF/EP quasi-isotropic $[45/-45/0/90]_s$ composite laminate ($475\text{ mm} \times 475\text{ mm} \times 1.275\text{ mm}$), depicted in Figure 1, was considered. Nine circular piezoelectric disks, 6.9 mm in diameter and 0.5 mm in thickness, were evenly surface-bonded on the laminate, numbered with P_i ($i=1, 2, \dots, 9$), which hypothetically partitioned each laminate into four quadrants. Up to 120 damage cases, suggested by a random function, were stochastically introduced, in which hole-type defects through the thickness with different locations and geometric identities were individually scattered in one quadrant. 3D finite element models for each individual presumed damage situation were created, employing 8-node consolidated solid brick elements with effective anisotropic laminate elastic properties, one of which is paradigmatically shown in Figure 2. Modelling techniques for the PZT actuators and sensors were developed [10]. The fundamental Lamb waves, conditioned with 5-cycle sinusoidal toneburst at the central energy of 0.5 MHz , were activated. While structural responses for wave propagation were simulated using ABAQUS/EXPLICIT[®] FEM code, and simultaneously monitored via each actuator-sensor path at a sampling rate of 20.48 MHz .

Figure 1. Composite laminate involving a hole-type damage

Figure 2. Ichnography of FEM model for the defective laminate shown in Figure 1

A signal processing package was developed based on a wavelet transform platform, targeted at extracting essential yet concise feature information, hereinafter named as ‘*Digital Damage Fingerprint*’ (DDF), to portray the complicated signal. It consists of units of signal purification, characterisation extraction, information compression and mapping. Illustratively, a sampled signal via actuator-sensor path $P5-P9$, with its corresponding filtered, compressed and extracted information, are

orderly displayed in Figure 3. The similar approach can be also applied to other actuator-sensor paths to construct a comprehensive set of ‘*Digital Damage Fingerprints*’ for a particular damage case.

Figure 3. Signal filtration, characterisation extraction and compression in the time domain

Via the proposed signal processing technique, it was observed that the acquired signal, preliminarily containing diverse broadband noisy interferences, could be depicted with brief extracted ‘*Digital Damage Fingerprint*’ in a compact data capacity, resulting in the dramatic decrease of computational cost for the training of neural network. Applying the approach to the individual damage cases, a damage parameter database (DPD) was then established, detailed in [10].

3. NETWORK TRAINING

A feedforward artificial neural network with two neural layers, possessing 36 and 14 neurons respectively, was designed. 2700 units were allocated in the input layer to host the extracted ‘*Digital Damage Fingerprints*’ for each damage case; while 6 damage indices, i.e., presence (indicated by 1 or 0), damage central location (ξ , ζ), semi-major/minor axes (α / β), and the orientation of major axis (ϕ , $0 \leq \phi < \pi$), were accommodated in the output layer. 120 sets of input vectors, corresponding to 120 chosen damage cases in one quadrant, and their associated outputs were created. All the layers were bridged by the log-sigmoid transfer functions. The network was trained using an error-backpropagation (BP) algorithm [11], and the training procedure was real-time monitored, shown in Figure 4. Wherein the network identification errors are noticed to be subject to the training iteration. An accelerated improvement on the identification can be manifestly observed at the initial training

stage as the iteration increases. Successive amendment persists and subdued convergence sustains after 250,000 iterations, which means the network reaches its stabilisation.

During the network development, all the damage cases were supposed to occur in one quadrant, so as to simplify the modelling and training while without missing the information that could possibly be captured with given efforts. A mapping technique was applied, involved in the processing package, to conveniently build up parallel networks for other quadrants [10]. Schematically, the basic flow for the network development is outline in Figure 5.

Figure 4. Convergence history for network training

Diagnosis A/B/C/D/E: identification using 20/30/40/60/80
damage cases for network training

Figure 5. Flowchart for network development

Figure 6. Graphic illustration for damage searching procedure

4. NETWORK VERIFICATION

Assisted with an active online damage diagnosis system on a *VXI* platform through *IEEE-488* bus [1], validity of the constructed artificial neural network was evaluated by quantitatively characterising hole-type damages in T650/F584 CF/EP [0/45/-45/90]_s quasi-isotropic laminates. Three specimens were manufactured and through-hole type defects with different locations and geometric identities were respectively introduced using a solid carbide helical router, respectively denoted by specimens 1[#], 2[#] and 3[#], summarised in Table 1. 9 Piezoelectric Lead Zirconate Titanate (PZT), 6.9 mm in diameter and 0.5mm in thickness, were surface-bonded on each laminate as actuators/sensors in accordance to the configuration in Figure 1.

Table 1. Specimen configurations (T650/F584 [0/45/-45/90]_s quasi-isotropic laminates)

Specimen No.	Geometric Dimension	Damage Indices					Zone
		To Left ¹ [mm]	To Btm ² [mm]	α [mm]	β [mm]	ϕ [°]	
SP1 [#]	475 × 475 × 1.275	269	192	17	11	175	2
SP2 [#]	475 × 475 × 1.275	172	272	19	12	135	4
SP3 [#]	475 × 475 × 1.275	330	353	25	18	40	3

1. Distance to the left edge from centre of the damage; 2. Distance to the bottom edge from centre of the damage; 3. Included angle between the major axis and bottom edge of the laminate

Coinciding with the network training, the same excitation and acquisition processes were followed. The experimentally acquired structural responses were applied with the signal processing package to eliminate diverse interferences and extract corresponding ‘Digital Damage Fingerprints’, which were then fed into the developed artificial neural network for damage assessment. The quantitative damage diagnosis for the chosen defective specimens were conclusively summarised in Table 2. While as a representative example, the visualised damage searching procedure for specimen 3[#] is compared with the actual damage in Figure 6. In the figure, a gradual approaching of the inferring to genuine damage is intuitively noticed with the increase of training patterns.

5. DISCUSSION

Being a complicated nonlinear mapping system, a neural network structure may offer various performances resting on its configurations.

Known as the deterministic factor to qualify the network capabilities, insufficient training patterns may lead to inaccurate prediction, while superfluous training is unavoidably at the cost of massive computational time. 50, 80, 100, 120 damage cases were respectively considered. As detailed in Table 1, it is noted that the identification precision is considerably dependent on the training patterns. More accurate identification originates from more training patterns. For the current system, 80 training patterns were found sufficient to quantitatively predict all damage indices. While no significant improvement is noticed when 100-120 training patterns were used, and moreover a slight impairment for damage orientation prediction and massive computing time were induced. Paradigmatically, the identification credibility for different damage indices versus training patterns is displayed in Figure 7.

Table 2. Diagnostic results

Training Patterns	Spec. No.	Prediction Error (%)				
		ξ	ζ	α	β	ϕ
50	1 [#]	17.5	13.5	17.4	15.5	27.7
	2 [#]	17.8	9.8	14.2	16.6	24.0
	3 [#]	15.7	11.0	12.3	14.1	26.5
80	1 [#]	6.5	3.5	6.9	5.8	9.2
	2 [#]	5.8	6.3	7.2	4.3	4.0
	3 [#]	6.5	3.1	4.6	3.8	4.3
100	1 [#]	5.7	3.2	6.0	5.0	8.5
	2 [#]	4.7	5.2	6.1	4.8	5.5
	3 [#]	5.0	3.7	2.8	3.5	4.1
120	1 [#]	5.3	3.7	4.8	4.8	9.1
	2 [#]	4.7	5.2	6.1	4.7	5.4
	3 [#]	5.0	3.0	2.8	3.0	8.1

(c) Specimen 3[#]

Figure 7. Network performances under different damage severities

Different transducer networks using 4, 6 and 8 activated PZTs, among the totally 9 transducers in the whole transducer network, were designed, respectively, engaging 4 (*P5-P9/P9-P5* and *P6-P8/P8-P6*), 8 (plus *P2-P9/P9-P2* and *P4-P9/P9-P4*), and 12 (plus *P3-P8/P8-P3* and *P6-P7/P7-P6*) actuator-sensor paths. Their diagnostic results, for Specimen 3[#] as an example, are summarised in Table 3.

Table 3. Identification precision for Specimen 3[#] using different transducer numbers

Number of PZT Transducers Used		4	6	8
Relative Identification Error (%)	ξ	18.7	9.4	6.5
	ζ	16.8	8.2	3.1
	α	24.5	17.5	4.6
	β	29.1	21.6	3.8
	ϕ	27.6	17.6	4.3

It is apparent that the a neural network of 4 PZT transducers is deficient in providing exact description for damage parameters; 6 PZT transducers are capable of approximately predicting the damage presence and location yet unwieldy to depict the damage shape exactly; while 8 PZT transducers are found adequate to quantitate the damage.

Various artificial neural network architectures, possessing 20/8, 36/14 and 50/30 neurons, were constructed, respectively. Their convergence history diagrams and corresponding visualised diagnostic results are compared in Figures 8 (a) and (b), respectively, where neither the neural network with deficient neurons nor the network containing superfluous neurons is satisfactory in predicting the damage. However at the moment, no explicit criteria exist to determine the most suitable network architecture for a system, while an efficient network can usually be achieved by trial-and-error method.

In addition to the major factors discussed hereinabove, the performances of a neural network-based damage identification approach is also influenced by the choice of initial weights and biases, the order of the input elements, the choice of transfer function and training function *etc.* (detailed in authors' another work [10]).

6. CONCLUDING REMARKS

A quantitative identification method for damages in CF/EP laminates was developed, using a supervised error-backpropagation artificial neural network (ANN) algorithm. Energy spectrographic characteristics of fundamental Lamb modes over a dual-parameter (time-frequency) space were purified and extracted for the network training, which are referred to as ‘*Digital Damage Fingerprints*’ (DDFs). A signal processing approach, consisting of signal filtration, characterisation extraction, signal compression and information mapping, was established, aimed at providing network sufficient yet compact training data. This technique was herein implemented by predicting damage indices for hole-type damages in quasi-isotropic composite laminate structures. Excellent identification for all damage indices (presence, location, geometry and orientation) has been achieved.

A wide range of factors were found to contribute to the identification accuracy. It is demonstrated that for the present system, the feedforward network with two neural processing layers, possessing 36 and 14 neurons and using the backpropagation algorithm, exhibits excellent prediction precision. No significant improvement on the identification was noticed for overtrained networks, which, moreover, consume massive computational time. The use of 8 PZT transducers is found to offer sufficient information for the exact online damage identification. However, to obtain an appropriate neural network configuration is a problem beyond the capability of mathematical evaluation and existing criteria or prototypes may be not universally applicable toward every specific system. The methodology developed in this study can readily be applied to other damage types. Meanwhile, the constructed structural health monitoring system may also be extended to engineering structures of other types of materials.

(a) Convergence history and stability

(b) Graphic illustration for diagnostic results

Figure 8. Identification precision under different network architectures

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